

Remotely Addressable Buttons with Can-Bus Data Path in Elevator Applications

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Abstract – CAN-Bus and its derivatives are widely used in many applications. In this study, CAN-Bus communication has been specifically developed for elevator buttons. Traditional elevator buttons have numerous cables to communicate with the control panel. However, buttons only help us call the elevator. Old-type buttons in high-rise buildings have a large number of cables. A large number of cables frequently cause malfunctions. CAN-Bus is a solution to reduce the number of cables. In contrast, faulty buttons based on CAN-Bus communication are irreparable due to software programming. This study presents a new button style that can be dynamically readdressed remotely and locally. Reducing the number of buttons provides significant efficiency in sales and profitability in the market. Data transmission based on the CAN-Bus also offers convenience in addressing and interactive solutions. In case of a malfunction, easy access to the button, reduced wiring, energy transmission on high floors, and cost savings are achieved. This system aims to design a low-cost and modular system that communicates via the CAN Bus, displaying information from multiple data sources (speed, temperature, fault codes, etc.) on a dot matrix display in real-time. Furthermore, CAN Bus communication dot matrix indicators provide ease of use in elevator systems for floor information, direction, error messages, and faults and current status occurring in the systems. It provides data transmission to passengers both inside and outside the cabin.

Keywords: CAN-Bus, Elevator, Button, Communication, Remotely Addressable

I. INTRODUCTION

Elevators are mechanical designs that move vertically on rails, emerging with the development of architecture, and used for transporting people and loads. Elevators, whose first examples began to appear

in the 17th century, provide the movement of passengers and loads from one floor to another vertically. Elevators are energized and moved from floor to floor via control cards and buttons. The movement of elevators and informing the user are done through buttons and indicators. There are buttons on each floor and indicator types determined by the need. The wiring system is done with one cable for each button on every floor and separate cables for each indicator segment on every floor. However, the labor involved in this basic connection is high and an economically incorrect choice [1,2]. Furthermore, the high number of cables also extends repair time. Therefore, reducing the number of cables will save labor, time, and money [3,4]. However, a reduced number of cables brings more programming load and the necessity for configuration. The CAN bus is a communication model widespread from automotive to industry, from medical to home applications [5-7]. The number of cables for the CAN bus is only two between two distant points. In elevator applications, the floor where the elevator is located is provided by indicators. Seven-segment displays are the simplest peripheral device between the digital world and the real world. To display the number "8", you need 7 data lines, and to display "0", you need 6 data lines [8,9]. Whereas with the CAN bus, 2 data lines are sufficient. The CAN bus has stronger aspects than similar hardware like RS-485, RS-232, RS-422 [10,11]. CAN bus applications can also be seen in elevators in the literature. This study focuses on the remote configuration of indicators or buttons and changing the characters to be displayed on the indicator in elevator applications and similar applications. With this study, less time loss and a more economical solution are aimed for.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Indicators and call buttons used on each floor in elevators may include warning bells and speech modules. Since some of these move with the cabin, having one of each is sufficient. However, buttons and indicators must be on every floor. In this study, the control of 8 buttons and indicators via the CAN bus was carried out.

STM32 series microcontrollers are very widely used ARM-based processors [12,13]. The program was made with the official compiler of the STM32F030. A picture of the settings made with Cube-MX for the STM32F030 is shown below in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Cube-MX settings menu for STM32F030

The block diagram of the modules designed in this study is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Block diagram of the system

The common point of the system is formed by the STM32F030 and the CAN bus integrated circuit. Although the indicator side is described as a 7-segment, it could also be a dot matrix or a similar module. The indicator is divided internally into a Dot Matrix design and driver (SMD LED & Driver), a CAN-based MCU (STM32), a DC-DC converter (MP2451), and a CAN Bus module (SN65HVD1050). The entire system is connected in parallel to each other and the line is terminated with a resistor. In CAN applications, it is 120 ohms [15,16]. As can be seen from Figure 2, the system is star-connected. If we disconnect a subscriber from the power stage or the CAN line, the system continues to work. For the system in Figure 3 to work, two types of software are needed. One is the software for remote access, and the other is the software that will run on the receivers.

(a)

```
void send_can_frame(void)
{
    canMsg_TX.Data[1] =
    canMsg_TX.Data[2] = canMsg_TX.Data[3] =
    canMsg_TX.Data[4] = canMsg_TX.Data[5] =
    canMsg_TX.Data[6] = canMsg_TX.Data[7] =
    0;

#define Frontdoor_call_registered
(0x000000c8) // Front door Hall call (
floor 200+floor )
#define Reardoor_call_registered
(0x00000108) // Rear door Hall call
(floor 264+floor )
```

(b)

Figure 3. (a) Control section of the interface program (b) C# send function for CAN data

Determine Message Priority: There are 8 priority values that can be set. 0 is the highest and 7 is the lowest priority value. The priority setting for all messages without a set priority is 3.

Determine Node Address: The node address on the CAN line is unique. In a network, a node address can only be given to a single node.

Select Message Sending Method: Message sending can be selected as point-to-point, periodic sending, or request sending.

Although the CAN protocol was initially used for electronic control systems in automobiles to communicate with each other over a single line, it quickly found application in different areas and gained rapid popularity worldwide [16,17]. CAN is an asynchronous real-time serial communication line with high performance and a powerful error prevention mechanism [18]. In elevator control systems, there are several units that communicate with each other using different methods. Classical systems use point-to-point wiring, and all units are connected directly to the main control panel. For example, for a 10-stop elevator system, there are approximately 30 cables from the control panel to the cabin unit and 20 cables to each floor push-button unit. This causes a lot of wiring and labor costs, causes difficulties when expanding the system, and increases the rate of incorrect connections. Serial communication seems to be the most effective solution in every aspect. CAN has been chosen as the serial communication bus due to its high reliability and cost-effectiveness. There are 3 different serial lines in elevator control systems. One line for communication between the control panel, cabin, and floor buttons; one line for communication between the control panel and sensors, speed control units; and one line for communication between control panels in group operations [19].

III. RESULTS

It is a low-cost and modular system that communicates via the CAN Bus and displays information from multiple data sources (speed, temperature, fault codes, etc.) on a dot matrix display in real-time. In this study, an application covering elevator buttons and indicators was carried out. In this application, made to reduce multiple elevator connections, an interface was written for the maintenance and adjustments arising from the reduction in the number of cables, ensuring the dynamism and flexibility of the system. This study is an applicable and realistic trial for elevators and can also guide future studies.

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